

DELAMINATION INSTABILITY IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY A SINGULAR HYBRID ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Delaminations in composite laminates severely reduce the compressive load bearing capacity of the structures. In particular, during the delamination post-buckling stage, crack opening would interact with the structural instability to form global and local out-of-plane deformations and load transfer. Stress concentration and geometrical nonlinearity involved make the problem complex.

Applying a variational principle to a modified hybrid functional and utilizing a rotated coordinate system, a singular hybrid element model is developed to include finite rotations in the analysis. For nonlinear analysis, a RIKS method is implemented into the simulation. Numerical results are given to demonstrate the solution accuracy and efficiency of the method. The effect of delamination length on the post-buckling behaviors and the fracture mode is also illustrated.

Keywords: delamination, buckling, post-buckling, hybrid finite element, finite rotations

1. INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar cracks which are formed between plies in composite laminates are often called delamination. It is well recognized that these cracks induce stress concentrations in the local regions and would severely deteriorate structural bearing capability under compressive loads. Delamination buckling and post-buckling have received considerable attention (e.g., Refs. [1-2]) in the aerospace and automotive industries. In particular, the compressive instability of crack growth would interact with the structural instability to form global and local out-of-plane deformations and load transfer between plies during the post-buckling stage. The problem combines mixed-mode fracture and geometrical nonlinearity in which finite displacements have to be considered.

A singular crack element surrounded by isoparametric eight-noded elements is used for analyzing the deformation patterns and complex stress states near the tip of a delamination crack. Applying a variational principle to a modified hybrid functional, the hybrid element method has been well developed for the case of small strains and infinitesimal rotations. Elasticity theory used in developing this special element is based on Lekhnitskii's complex variable potentials [3] and the method of eigenfunction expansion. To account for finite rotations in the post-buckling analysis, a rotated coordinate system is instituted at the crack tip of the hybrid element and a rotation tensor is calculated from the surrounding isoparametric elements. The total deformation is thus the superposition of the small rotation solution and the deformation resulting from finite rotations. To improve numerical efficiency in searching an equilibrium path, a RIKS method for computing either load or displacement increment is implemented into the numerical scheme for geometric nonlinearity.

Numerical results will be given for a unidirectional composite plate with a through-width delamination to illustrate the solution accuracy and the efficiency of the present analysis. We also discuss the effects of (1) stepping schemes involved in nonlinear analysis, (2) the assigned tolerance for convergence, (3) eigenfunction truncation in the hybrid element, and (4) the hybrid element size, on the numerical solutions of deformation and stress intensity factors (K_I and K_{II}). Finally, the possible mode of crack growth for two different delamination lengths is examined.

2. FORMULATIONS

Introducing a rotational coordinate system at the crack tip in formulating the problem, deformation displacement and its gradient will be small with respect to the rotated coordinate system. The finite element method based on the anisotropic laminate elasticity [3] and a modified hybrid variational functional for small strains and infinitesimal rotations [4] can then be applied to the problem. The tensors associated with the rotation can be calculated from the averages from the isoparametric elements surrounding the singular hybrid element.

2.1. Laminate Elasticity Solution

Assuming that a unidirectional composite plate as shown in Figure 1 has infinite width in the z-direction, one could consider it as a homogeneous orthotropic body under generalized plane deformation. Based on this assumption, all the planes in the z-direction remain plane, and thus all stresses and displacements would be functions of x and y only. Without body forces, the equilibrium equation combined with compatibility condition can be written in terms of a stress function $F(x,y)$ as

$$L_4 F(x,y) = \left[\tilde{S}_{22} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^4} + (2\tilde{S}_{12} + \tilde{S}_{66}) \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \tilde{S}_{11} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial y^4} \right] F(x,y) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{S}_{ij} = S_{ij} - S_{i3}S_{j3}/S_{33}$ ($i,j = 1,2,6$) is the reduced compliance matrix for an anisotropic body. The homogeneous solution of the stress function $F(x,y)$ to Equation 1 shown by Lekhnitskii is of the form

$$F(x,y) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \hat{F}_k(z_k) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \hat{F}_k(x + \mu_k y) \quad (2)$$

where μ_k 's are two pairs of pure imaginary conjugate roots (i.e. $\mu_3 = \bar{\mu}_1$ and $\mu_4 = \bar{\mu}_2$) of the algebraic equation

$$\tilde{S}_{11}\mu^4 + (2\tilde{S}_{12} + \tilde{S}_{66})\mu^2 + \tilde{S}_{22} = 0 \quad (3)$$

One particular choice of \hat{F}_k to satisfy Equation 1 is given in Reference [5] as

$$\hat{F}_k(z_k) = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{C_{kn} z_k^{\delta_n + 2}}{(\delta_n + 1)(\delta_n + 2)} \quad (4)$$

where C_{kn} and δ_n are constants to be determined, and N is the number of δ_n 's included in the expansion. Using the formula

$$\sigma_x \equiv \sigma_1 = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2}, \quad \sigma_y \equiv \sigma_2 = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2}, \quad \tau_{xy} \equiv \sigma_6 = -\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (5)$$

and the stress-strain equation for orthotropic materials, the stress and displacement fields can be determined:

$$\sigma_i = 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^2 \left[\Lambda_{ik} C_{kn} z_k^{\delta_n} + \bar{\Lambda}_{ik} C_{(k+2)n} \bar{z}_k^{\delta_n} \right] \quad (i = 1,2,6) \quad (6)$$

$$u_i = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^2 \left[\Gamma_{ik} C_{kn} z_k^{\delta_n+1} + \bar{\Gamma}_{ik} C_{(k+2)n} \bar{z}_k^{\delta_n+1} \right] / (\delta_n + 1) \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (7)$$

where $\Lambda_{1k} = \mu_k^2$, $\Lambda_{2k} = 1$, $\Lambda_{6k} = -\mu_k$, $\Gamma_{1k} = \bar{S}_{11}\mu_k^2 + \bar{S}_{12}$, $\Gamma_{2k} = \bar{S}_{12}\mu_k + \bar{S}_{22}/\mu_k$. Applying the near-field traction boundary condition on the fully open crack surfaces leads to a standard eigenvalue problem which determines eigenvalues δ_n 's. To have finite values for displacement, these eigenvalues must satisfy the condition $\text{Re}[\delta_n] > -1$, where Re represents the real part of δ_n . Once the eigenvalues are determined, the corresponding eigenvectors C_{kn} can be evaluated.

2.2. Singular Hybrid Finite Element Formulation

The hybrid finite element approach requires that the stress and displacement tensors, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and \mathbf{u} , within the element and the displacement along the boundary, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$, be independently assumed. For distinct real δ_n 's, since the general expressions for stress and displacement have been derived in last section, their finite element formulations can then be written as

$$\sigma_i = 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \beta_n \left(\sum_{k=1}^2 \text{Re}[f_{ik}^n(z_k)] \right) \quad (i = 1, 2, 6) \quad (8)$$

$$u_i = 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \beta_n \left(\sum_{k=1}^2 \text{Re}[g_{ik}^n(z_k)] \right) \quad (i = 1, 2) \quad (9)$$

where β_n 's are real constants to be determined in the finite element formulation, and f_{ik}^n and g_{ik}^n are known eigenfunctions obtained from Equations 6 and 7. Using Equations 8 and 9, the element stresses, boundary tractions, and displacement inside the element can be expressed in a matrix form as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\beta}, \quad \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{R}\boldsymbol{\beta}, \quad \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} = \{\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots\}$. To maintain displacement compatibility across the boundary of adjacent elements, the displacement along the element boundary is represented in terms of nodal displacement vector $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ as

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{L}\hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{L} is a matrix of proper shape functions chosen for the boundary of the hybrid elements. Following the procedure of deriving hybrid finite elements described in Reference [6], the modified functional is obtained as

$$\pi_{mh} = -\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{G} \hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (12)$$

in which

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A} (\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{R}) dS \quad \mathbf{G} = \int_{\partial A} \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{L} dS \quad (13)$$

Taking variation of functional π_{mh} with respect to $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ yields the relation between $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{G} \hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (14)$$

and the functional becomes

$$\pi_{mh} = \frac{1}{2} \hat{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{G} \hat{\mathbf{q}} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \hat{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{K}_L \hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (15)$$

Because of finite rotations involved in the problem, a rotational coordinate system is introduced into the hybrid finite element formulation so that the nodal displacement vector in the rotated coordinate system, $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$, is related to the global displacement vector \mathbf{q} by a rotation tensor \mathbf{Q} as

$$\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{Q}\hat{\mathbf{q}} \quad (16)$$

Equation 16 can then be rewritten as

$$\pi_{mh} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{q} \quad (17)$$

The tangent stiffness matrix for nonlinear analyses corresponding to the given functional is obtained by taking twice the derivatives of π_{mh} with respect to the nodal displacement \mathbf{q} :

$$\mathbf{K}_T = \frac{\partial^2 \pi_{mh}}{\partial \mathbf{q}^T \partial \mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_{G1} + \mathbf{K}_{G2} + \mathbf{K}_{G3} \quad (18)$$

where

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{Q}^T \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{G1} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{Q}^T + \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{B}^T \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{G2} = 2 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{q} \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{G3} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}_L \mathbf{B}^T \quad (22)$$

and

$$A_{ijk} = \frac{\partial Q_{jk}}{\partial q_i} \quad B_{ik} = q_m \frac{\partial Q_{mk}}{\partial q_i} \quad (23)$$

One way to search for the stable load-displacement path is to perform incremental analysis using the nonlinear formulations. For a continuum subjected to a single loading, the incremental form of the equilibrium equation can be written as

$$\mathbf{K}_T \dot{\mathbf{q}} = \dot{\lambda} \mathbf{P} \quad (24)$$

where \mathbf{P} is the vector for the applied nodal force, λ is the single loading parameter, and the dot above the symbols represents the increment of the variables. This equation will be used to calculate buckling load, and load or displacement increment for each step during the post-buckling stage. After the displacement solution \mathbf{q} is obtained, stresses at any point within the singular hybrid element can be computed by Equations 10, 14, and 16. Stress intensity factors for the delamination cracks are then determined by

$$K_I = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} r^{-\delta_s} \sigma_y(r, 0) = 2\beta_1 \sum_{k=1}^2 \text{Re}(C_{k1}) \quad (25)$$

$$K_{II} = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} r^{-\delta_s} \tau_{xy}(r, 0) = -2\beta_1 \sum_{k=1}^2 \text{Re}(C_{k1} \mu_k) \quad (26)$$

where δ_s is the eigenvalue corresponding to the stress singularity and β_1 is the stress parameter associated with δ_s in the formulation. Note that δ_s equals -1/2 for problems studied in this paper.

2.3. Finite Element Nonlinear Analysis

To deal with geometrical nonlinearity in post-buckling analysis, a RIKS method [7] is implemented into the simulation. The RIKS approach is a scheme of Newton type aided by an arc-length constraint in searching the equilibrium path. For each step, the displacement and load increments at the i -th iteration, $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(i)}$ and $\dot{\lambda}_{(i)}$, are restricted by

$$\| \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(i)} \|^2 + | \dot{\lambda}_{(i)} |^2 = (\Delta s)^2 \quad (i = 0, 1, 2, \dots) \quad (27)$$

load increment $\dot{\lambda}_{(0)}$ or displacement increment $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(0)}$ is specified.

3. RESULTS

Accuracy and efficiency of the present model is demonstrated in terms of stress intensity factors and deformation patterns at the post-buckling stage for a delaminated unidirectional composite plate. For all the calculations, elastic properties and geometry of the plate listed in Tables 1 and 2 are employed, and boundary conditions $u_y=0$ and $\partial u_x/\partial y = 0$ are applied at $x = \pm L$ (Fig. 1). A mesh of 489 elements and 1601 nodes is used except for studying element size effect, and the hybrid element is always square in shape. The average buckling loads (P_b 's) obtained for delamination crack lengths $a = 16.38$ mm and 32.77 mm are 4.264 KN and 1.135 KN respectively, and the load vs. end displacement (shortening at $x = \pm L$) behaviors during post-buckling are delineated by Fig. 2. Convergence study for the singular hybrid element is concluded by evaluating the effects of convergence margin, eigenfunction truncation, and element size on the solutions. For each of the effects, the behaviors of load vs. lateral displacement and stress intensity factors vs. end displacement are presented. For lateral displacements, v_1 represents the out-of-plane displacement at the top surface on the centerline, while v_2 gives the one at the bottom face. A crack with length $a = 16.38$ mm is first considered in the convergence study as follows.

Computation tends to be more efficient if mixed force/displacement stepping scheme is implemented. For displacement stepping, the displacement difference of the previous two steps is used for the initial where Δs is a pre-selected length in the λ - \mathbf{q} Euclidean space. Using the notations for displacement and load updates at every step

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(n)} = \Delta \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(n)} + \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(0)} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\lambda}_{(n)} = \Delta \dot{\lambda}_{(n)} + \dot{\lambda}_{(0)} \quad (28)$$

a system of equations for the nonlinear analysis can be obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_T & -\mathbf{P} \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(n)}^T & \dot{\lambda}_{(n)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(n)} \\ \Delta \dot{\lambda}_{(n)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the residual force vector. This system of equations can be solved only if either the initial increment of the step, i.e. $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_{(0)}$. The results shown in Figure 3 indicate that the calculations by force-only stepping and by force/displacement stepping are essentially the same. The convergence criterion we have chosen is $\text{Max}(\Delta \dot{q}_j)/\dot{q}_j \leq \epsilon$ for all displacement components. From Figure 4, we found very little discrepancy in the solutions for ϵ varied from 0.05 to 0.001. The effects of eigenfunction truncation are illustrated by Figure 5. To obtain reliable results, thirteen or more terms ($N \geq 13$) are required in the eigenfunction expansion.

For analyses with finite rotations, rotations for the hybrid element are determined from its surrounding isoparametric elements. Therefore, the hybrid element and its adjacent elements of smaller size may be necessary for the calculated rotations be representative of the hybrid element. A nondimensional parameter is defined to characterize the size of the hybrid element

$$\eta = \Delta h/h \quad (30)$$

where $2\Delta h$ is the edge length of a square hybrid element and h is defined in Figure 1. It is observed in Figure 6 that the deformation patterns are not sensitive to the hybrid element size, however decreasing the element size is critical for accurate stress intensity factors. The maximum percentage difference in stress intensity factors between $\eta=1/8$ and $\eta=1/10$, which occurs at end displacement equal to 0.2 mm, is 3.2% for K_I and 3.4% for K_{II} .

To illustrate the influence of crack length on the out-of-plane displacements and load transfer during the post-buckling stage, an initial delamination crack length $a = 32.77$ mm which is twice the size of the previous study is investigated. By a delamination size increase, the maximum load capacity of the composite is reduced as seen from Fig. 2, and a prominent difference of deformation patterns and stress intensity factors can be obtained and is shown in Fig. 7. In contrast to the case of $a = 16.38$ mm, v_1 as well as K_I continuously increases, while K_{II} runs in a different direction and reaches a maximum at the end displacement ≈ 0.1 mm.

Fig. 1. Schematic of a delaminated unidirectional composite plate.

Table 1. Elastic properties for a transversely isotropic composite plate.

E_{11} (GPa)	42.1
E_{22} (GPa)	10.0
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.261
ν_{23}	0.381
G_{12} (GPa)	4.00

Table 2. Geometry of a delaminated composite plate used for the convergence study.

L (mm)	63.5
H (mm)	3.302
h (mm)	0.6604

Fig. 2. Load vs. end displacement behaviors for 16.38 mm and 32.77 mm delamination.

Fig. 3. The effects of stepping algorithm on (a) load-displacement (b) stress intensity factors.

Fig. 4. The effects of convergence tolerance on (a) load-displacement (b) stress intensity factors.

Fig 5. The effects of eigenfunction truncations on (a) load-displacement (b) stress intensity factors.

Fig. 6. The effects of hybrid element size on (a) load-displacement (b) stress intensity factors.

Fig. 7. (a) Deformation patterns, and (b) stress intensity factors for a crack of length = 32.77 mm.

4. SUMMARY

In this research, a singular hybrid element model with finite rotations is developed for analyzing delamination buckling and post-buckling of composite laminates. A RIKS method combined with a force/displacement stepping algorithm is implemented to trace the post-buckling equilibrium path. Based on the singular hybrid element, the results for deformation and detailed stress fields near the crack tip show great solution accuracy and numerical efficiency in modeling this class of problems. The influence of flow size on the maximum load capacity and the variation of K_I and K_{II} is also demonstrated. The effects of crack length and location on the delamination instability and growth using an appropriate mixed-mode fracture criterion are currently under investigation.

5. REFERENCES

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